

diluted split-sample to 18×10^6 sperm/ml with 10% autologous SP to 100 ml in three different extender media: BTS (Control), modified pH-stabilized BTS (mBTS) and pH-stabilized Androstar® Plus (APlus; Minitüb, Germany). Samples were stored for 144 h at 17°C. Data were tested for normal distribution (Shapiro-Wilk test) followed by pair-wise comparisons using Student t-test (PROC UNIVARIATE) with SAS Enterprise Guide 7.1. Spermatozoa extended in BTS from two boars reacted sensitive to their own SP as seen in low motility (13.1%, 7.2%) assessed with AndroVision® and a low proportion of viable sperm with high mitochondria membrane potential (hMMP) assessed by flow cytometry with propidium iodide and JC-1 (60.3%, 27.4%). The other six boars maintained high sperm quality in BTS-extended semen during storage (motility: 74.0 ± 3.8 %, hMMP: 87.6 ± 4.8 %). Semen of the two SP-sensitive boars extended in APlus maintained high motility (74.1%, 65.1%) and hMMP (97.7%, 84.9%), whereas mBTS-extended samples showed similar low values for both sperm traits (motility: 4.3%, 10.9%; hMMP: 19.2%, 36.5%) as samples extended in BTS. In conclusion, in boars with an enhanced sensitivity of sperm to autologous SP, the protective long-term extender medium APlus can counteract the detrimental effect on sperm during long-term storage. This effect is independent of pH-stabilization in the sample.

P95 | Stimulation of follicle maturation in the parent flock of hens

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During the oviposition period, the ovaries contain from 500 to 3500 follicles of varying degrees of maturity. The purpose of our research was to study the process of stimulating the maturation of follicles in the parent flock of hens using a betulin (birch extract) nanoemulsion. To conduct the study two groups were formed: control and experimental (betulin emulsion 1 ml per head daily for 30 days). The research methods are biochemical and morphometric. As a result of the anatomic cutting, it was recorded that the test group of hens had uniform formation of secondary follicles (45–30 mm diameter), 4–5 follicles, which corresponds to the norm for high-laying hens with daily ovulation. Betulin accelerates the processes of metabolism and lipid excretion from the body, including through the egg, which confirms the data on the content of vitamin A (retinyl acetate) in the yolk, 6634 IU/kg in the experimental group and 4885 IU/kg in the control. Betulin contributed to the inhibition of cholesterol catabolism and inhibition of lipid synthesis in the liver: a decrease in abdominal fat deposition by 35% was observed (in the experimental group, 75.8 g and in the control 116.8 g); a decrease in liver mass by 29% (51 g in the experimental and 72 g in the control group). The control group showed the following results – 1/3 of

the livestock had 8 – 9 secondary follicles and 2/3 of the livestock 1–3 secondary follicles. These figures indicate uneven maturation of secondary follicles. Indicators in live body weight confirmed the effect of betulin; in the experimental group, the rate was lower on average by 3.2%. It seems that the use of the betulin nanoemulsion has contributed to the stimulation of follicle formation due to the redistribution of lipid deposits in the body.

P96 | Calcification in organs of the reproductive system of broiler parent flocks

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Failure of the reproductive system of the breeding bird leads to a decrease in egg production and significant losses. The purpose of this study was to establish the causes of calculus and calcifications in the reproductive organs of the parent broiler flock and also to reduce the percentage of their occurrence. In the study, 2 groups of 8000 heads were formed: control (basic) and experimental (the bird additionally received probiotic based on *Bacillus subtilis* bacteria at the rate of 2 kg/1 ton of feed). Morphological, histological, biochemical and electron microscopic methods were used. Numerous pathological changes in the reproductive organs were recorded in the control group of hens and roosters. Calcifications detected in the ovaries and oviducts in 7% of the population led to stagnation in the reproductive organs, chronic inflammation and created the prerequisites of infection. In 10% of the population, it was revealed that productivity was reduced by 4.7% due to violation of egg formation. Ultrastructural changes in the permeability of mitochondrial membranes of spermatozoa in the form of calculus were established. A decrease in the quality of sperm was found in 50% of cases, the culling of the livestock of roosters was 35%. In the experimental group of hens and roosters receiving *Bacillus subtilis*, pathological changes due to calcification have not been identified. As a result, the main reasons for the occurrence of calculus and calcinate are a violation of the feeding schemes, the incorrect selection of calcium-containing additives for age and sex groups and the use of water with a high content of carbonates. To preserve the reproductive capacity of the birds it is necessary to observe feeding options and use of probiotics.